

Tackling mental health disorders, burnout, workplace violence, post-traumatic stress disorders amidst climate change, and new global challenges: The crucial role of emotional management education

Francesco CHIRICO^{1*}, Amelia RIZZO²

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¹*Faculty of Medicine and Surgery, Post-graduate School in Occupational Health, Catholic University of the Sacred Heart, Rome, Italy.*

E-mail: medlavchirico@gmail.com ORCID: 0000-0002-8737-4368

²*Department of Clinical and Experimental Medicine, University of Messina, Italy. E-mail: amrizzo@unime.it ORCID: 0000-0002-6229-6463*

**Correspondence*

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Dear Readers,

In today's rapidly evolving world, emotional management education is crucial across various aspects of life, from addressing workplace challenges like violence, stress, and burnout syndrome to navigating global issues such as climate change and ongoing conflicts [1,2].

Programs that teach emotional regulation are essential in enhancing workplace productivity and harmony by helping employees manage stress and conflict and boosting societal resilience against external crises. These programs significantly benefit vulnerable groups who are disproportionately affected by global challenges, including the elderly, children, and those with psychological conditions [3].

One effective technique in training courses planned by our scientific association, the “*International Network for the Advancement of Medicine, Psychology, and Public Health*,” is tapping, also known as Emotional Freedom Techniques (EFT), which

involves tapping specific points on the body to reduce emotional distress [4]. It is a scientifically supported, practical tool that can significantly reduce symptoms of anxiety, depression, and post-traumatic stress disorder. Tapping is a form of psychological acupressure based on the principles of both ancient Chinese acupressure and modern psychology. It involves tapping with your fingertips on specific meridian points on the body while focusing on negative emotions or physical sensations. This combination of tapping the energy meridians and voicing positive affirmations works to clear the emotional block from your body's bioenergy system, thus restoring your mind and body's balance.

The process is simple and can be done anywhere. It typically involves several rounds of tapping on each point, usually starting at the top of the head, moving down to the eyebrow, side of the eye, under the eye, under the nose, the chin, the collarbone, under the arm, and finishing at the top of the head again. Users of tapping believe that it helps reduce stress or traumatic stress by sending signals to the part of the brain that controls stress (the amygdala) and helps regulate the body's energy.

It is used to treat a wide array of psychological and physical issues, from anxiety and depression to chronic pain and insomnia. It has been gaining popularity due to its simplicity and the rapid relief it can provide.

Besides tapping, our programs also focus on mindfulness, cognitive restructuring, and resilience building, providing a comprehensive approach to emotional management.

An important technique often introduced in emotional management courses is Mindfulness Meditation. This practice involves focusing on the present moment while calmly acknowledging and accepting one's feelings, thoughts, and bodily sensations. As a therapeutic technique, mindfulness helps individuals become more aware of their thoughts and feelings so that instead of being overwhelmed, they can better manage them [5].

Practicing mindfulness can significantly reduce the symptoms of psychological stress, anxiety, and depression. It can also improve physical health by lowering blood pressure, enhancing sleep, and alleviating gastrointestinal difficulties. In a workplace or educational setting, mindfulness training helps participants improve their concentration and attention, increase self-awareness, and handle interpersonal challenges more effectively.

Spirituality profoundly influences emotional well-being by providing individuals with a sense of purpose and perspective that can enhance resilience against emotional turmoil. Techniques such as mindfulness meditation, prayer, and other spiritual practices like chanting or meditative walking help cultivate a moment-by-moment awareness, a connection with the divine, or alignment with personal values. These practices offer a structured way to articulate and alleviate emotional burdens, promote mental calmness, reduce stress, and foster a supportive community. Integrating spirituality into daily life can significantly improve emotional insight, reduce symptoms of mental health disorders, and increase overall life satisfaction, making it a powerful tool for enhancing psychological health.

We actively seek scientific contributions on these topics and encourage universities, institutions, and associations interested in joining our network to collaborate and expand our collective understanding and impact. By integrating these emotional management techniques into educational curriculums and professional development initiatives, we aim to foster healthier, more resilient communities and workplaces, underscoring the need for more organizations to recognize its value as a cornerstone of personal well-being and broader societal health.

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